

The evolution of EU competition law and policy in the pharmaceutical sector: long-lasting impacts of a pandemic

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ABSTRACT

This article investigates the evolution of the European Union (EU) competition law and policy enforcement in the pharmaceuticals sector, focusing on the impact of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) crisis as a turning point. Before COVID-19, EU competition authorities' goals and priorities focused on pay-for-delay agreements between originators and generic pharmaceutical undertakings. During COVID-19, the European Commission developed soft laws (such as temporary frameworks and comfort letters) enabling undertakings to cooperate to increase access to essential health products and COVID-19 vaccines. In the post-pandemic era, initiatives like the Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe, the Single Market Emergency Instrument (SMEI), the Health Emergency Response Authority (HERA), the compulsory licensing proposal and the upcoming changes in the pharmaceutical regulations reflect a patient-centred approach and diverse agenda. This article underscores the move towards a more inclusive EU competition law and policy framework in the pharmaceutical sector as part of this evolution.

KEYWORDS: EU competition law; competition policy; pharmaceutical sector; COVID-19; post-pandemic

JEL CLASSIFICATIONS: K21, I18, L65, L41

1. INTRODUCTION

The pharmaceutical industry is unique in its position at the nexus of multiple disciplines and plays an important role in the healthcare sector, driving innovation, developing life-saving medicines, and contributing to public health.

to allow arrangements between originators and generic undertakings by issuing comfort letters.¹⁴ Although this approach led to evergreening the branded product and creating a significant entry barrier for generic products, it was defended by pro-innovation arguments. This can be seen, for example, in *Elsa/Pfizer* (1999), in which their agreement regarding the co-promotion and co-marketing of Alzheimer's therapy drugs led to a dominant position in many Member States and raised competition law concerns. Still, the European Commission cleared the case by issuing a comfort letter for seven years because of the consumer benefits¹⁵ of the agreement.¹⁶ Another example of this flexibility from the Commission's perspective is the *Pfizer+ Hoechst Marion Roussel AG* (1999) case, in which these two pharmaceutical companies entered into several agreements to produce and distribute inhalable insulin to compete with the classic injectable insulin in the market. They also agreed to market that product internationally. The European Commission issued a comfort letter and exempted the agreement from the application of Article 81(1) EC. However, following the inquiry, the Commission changed its stance dramatically.¹⁷

After statistics on originator and generic pharmaceutical producers and the probability of anticompetitive practices raised some concerns about hampering competition in the market,¹⁸ the European Commission initiated a sector inquiry into the EU pharmaceuticals sector in January 2008. Following an exhaustive investigation, the Commission released its final report in 2009,¹⁹ published some annual brief monitoring reports, and released a comprehensive report in 2019.²⁰ The latest Commission report on pharmaceuticals was published in 2024²¹ and the evolving nature and the enforcement trend of competition law enforcement in this sector can easily be seen in these reports. The investigation looked into the regulatory system, trademarks, marketing authorizations, pricing, and reimbursement to determine if companies engaged in anticompetitive practices to delay²² or prevent competition in generic pharmaceutical markets.²³

Lundbeck²⁴ was the European Commission's first pay-for-delay decision and a milestone for enforcing competition law in the pharmaceutical sector. The Commission fined Lundbeck €93.8 million for entering into the pay-for-delay scheme that delayed the sale of generic Citalopram. Furthermore, the generic companies were fined a combined

¹⁴ A Comfort Letter is a helpful tool for undertakings to get assurance from competition authorities that a particular action does not raise concerns for competition law. See David Henry and Jacques Buhart, 'COVID-20: The Comfort Letter Is Dead. Long Live the Comfort Letter?' (2020), 43 *World Compet*, 305.

¹⁵ In the European Commission's case law, some horizontal cooperations are not considered hard-core cartels: See Niamh Dunne and Imelda Maher, 'The "Acceptable" Cartel? Horizontal Agreements within EU Competition Law: Introduction' (2020) 65 *Abull* 335.

¹⁶ Case IV/36.393/F3-EISAI/Pfizer (notification of a cooperation agreement) [1995] OJ C36/5.

¹⁷ Soren Zinck, 'Pay for Delay?' (2013) 33 *Pharm Exec* 20, 21.

¹⁸ Companies that produce 'generic' versions of those same products can sell their versions without paying royalties to the original patent holder, making them anywhere from 20 to 90 per cent less expensive. See Suzanne Dunne and others, 'A Review of the Differences and Similarities between Generic Drugs and Their Originator Counterparts, Including Economic Benefits Associated with Usage of Generic Medicines, Using Ireland as a Case Study' (2013) 14 *BMC Pharmacol Toxicol* 1; Ben Teasdale, David Light and Kevin A Schulman, 'Price and Quality in the Generic Pharmaceutical Market' (2022) 145 *Circulation* 1185.

¹⁹ EU Pharmaceutical Sector Inquiry, final report, adaptation date: 8 July 2009 <https://ec.europa.eu/competition/sec_tors/pharmaceuticals/inquiry/staff_working_paper_part1.pdf> S20, accessed 14 June 2024.

²⁰ European Commission, 'Competition Enforcement in the Pharmaceutical Sector (2009-2017): European Competition Authorities Working Together for Affordable and Innovative Medicines' COM (2019) 17 final.

²¹ European Commission, 'Update on Competition Enforcement in the Pharmaceutical Sector (2018-2022)' (2024) Report from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament.

²² See More Bakhoun, 'Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs), Competition Law and Excessive Pricing of Medicines' in Carlos M Correa and Reto M Hilty (eds), *Access to Medicines and Vaccines: Implementing Flexibilities Under Intellectual Property Law* (Springer Nature 2022) 283.

²³ *ibid.*

²⁴ A 2002 pay-for-delay agreement between a Danish pharmaceutical company (Lundbeck) and the four generic manufacturers (Alpharma, Merck KGaA/Generics UK, Arrow, and Ranbaxy) aiming to ban cheaper generic versions of Lundbeck's popular antidepressant Citalopram from entering the European market was investigated by the Commission.

Commission's decision, Teva and Cephalon's pay-for-delay agreement is considered a breach of Article 101 TFEU. The Commission fined them €60.5 million for entering into a pay-for-delay agreement on 26 November 2020.³⁹ Pay-for-delay agreements were popular trends in the EU competition law enforcement from 2008 until the COVID-19 pandemic. Similarly, the new Teva Copaxone lawsuit raises antitrust concerns about abuse of dominance and patent abuse. The European Commission released a Statement of Objections on 10 October 2022, suggesting that Teva may have engaged in anticompetitive conduct in numerous European markets for multiple sclerosis drug glatiramer acetate. The Commission found that Teva hindered the market entry and uptake of competitive glatiramer acetate products to prolong Copaxone's exclusivity. The Commission's preliminary assessment reveals that Teva staggered filed divisional patent applications with significantly overlapping content with the European Patent Office. Teva allegedly impeded patent review by withdrawing parent patent applications when competitors seeking market entry disputed them. Thus, competitors had to fight comparable patent claims for each divisional patent, extending legal ambiguity and preventing generic or generic drugs from entering the market.⁴⁰

The focus of enforcement gradually shifted over time. The relationship between intellectual property rights and antitrust laws and how an access-based approach to patent cases over a mere market approach is needed, especially during a health crisis, was a hot debate. Where pay-for-delay agreements had long dominated discussions, excessive pricing emerged as a rising issue. The pandemic underscored its importance as a concern, with debates continuing in its aftermath.⁴¹ Access to medicine, the need for a patient-centred pharmaceutical sector, and the evergreening of pharmaceuticals are closely related to excessive pricing.

The Aspen case⁴² is the Commission's first decision regarding prohibiting excessive pricing under Article 102(a) TFEU, using the United Brand's framework.⁴³ On 15 May 2017, the European Commission began formal antitrust proceedings against Aspen based on some facts, such as that Aspen raised the prices of six cancer drugs. Based on Article 9 of Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2003,⁴⁴ Aspen offered some commitments to resolve the Commission's competitive concerns.⁴⁵ The difference between Aspen and previous decisions in this arena is that the focus has shifted from branded pharmaceutical producers to generic manufacturers. If competition law infringements are essential because they create a barrier to entry for generics, competition law also meddles when generic companies raise prices.

Anticompetitive practices in the pharmaceutical sector are interconnected. Gallasch argues that pay-for-delay agreements can 'facilitate a broader unilateral strategy' of pharmaceutical undertakings such as product hopping.⁴⁶ Excessive pricing could result from product

³⁹ Case COM/AT 39686 Cephalon, European Commission: Antitrust: Commission fines Teva and Cephalon €60.5 for delaying the entry of cheaper generic medicine <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_2220> accessed 14 June 2024. C/2020/8153, OJ C 32, 29.1.2021, 9–10.

⁴⁰ European Commission (n 21) 22.

⁴¹ Excessive pricing can be illegal under competition law if it arises from abusing dominant positions or anticompetitive agreements. Case law of the European Court of Justice supports this view, ruling that excessive pricing can be considered an abuse of a dominant position if it harms consumer interests or hinders competition. See Llan Akker and Wolf Sauter, 'Excessive pricing of pharmaceuticals in EU law: balancing competition, innovation and regulation' in Pier L Parcu, Giorgio Monti and Marco Botta (eds), *The Interaction of Competition Law and Sector Regulation*. (Edward Elgar 2022) 233–58.

⁴² On 10 February 2021, the Commission announced that Aspen must cut prices on six cancer drugs by 73 per cent in Europe and secure a long-term supply of off-patent medicines

⁴³ Harald Mische 'The EU Aspen Decision: The European Commission's First Excessive Pricing Decision in the Pharmaceutical Market' in Wolf Sauter, Marcel Canoy and Jotte Muler (eds), *EU Competition Law and Pharmaceuticals* (Edward Elgar 2022) 171.

⁴⁴ Regulation 1/2003 OJ L1/1, 4 January 2003.

⁴⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/competition/antitrust/cases/dec_docs/40394/40394_4303_6.pdf> accessed 14 June 2024. Diletta Danieli, 'Excessive Pricing in the Pharmaceutical Industry: Adding Another String to the Bow of EU Competition Law' (2021) 16 Health Econ Policy Law 64.

⁴⁶ Sve Gallasch, 'A New Dimension to EU Pharma Antitrust Product Hopping and Unilateral Pay for Delay' (2016) 12 *Eur Compet J* 137.

hopping, in which pharmaceutical companies extend the exclusivity period for branded products. Disparagement practices are also connected to pay-for-delay agreements and excessive pricing. This practice usually promotes the company's original medicine and/or its generic product.⁴⁷ In Sanofi's case, the advertising strategy of this company was found to be misleading regarding the quality and safety of a generic blood-thinning drug (Plavix(R)), according to the French Competition Authority decision in 2010.⁴⁸ Although most cases involving disparagement practices in European competition law have been investigated nationally, in June 2022, the Commission started formally investigating disparagement practices for Vifor Pharma. The Vifor case is still under scrutiny by the Commission regarding Viofer Pharma's dominance in the intravenous iron treatment market. Having a calculated strategy for disseminating misleading safety information regarding its main competitor, Monofer, to healthcare professionals might be considered an abuse of dominance under Article 102 TFEU.⁴⁹

Off-label use of drugs, which refers to using them for purposes other than those listed in the approved information by regulatory agencies, is another practice which is closely connected to disparagement practices and could be a competition law violation⁵⁰ and, in some cases, such as Hoffmann-La Roche (2018), might even consider a 'restriction of competition by the object' under Article 102 TFEU. In this case,⁵¹ Roche and Novartis agreed to reduce the demand for Avastin (a product developed by Roche) for ophthalmology purposes in favour of Lucentis (a product licensed by and marketed by Novartis). Pharmaceutical companies disseminated information about Avastin's increased risks and decreased effectiveness for eye treatments without scientific proof. Both companies were found to violate Article 101 TFEU by the Italian competition authority by disseminating misleading information and disparagement practices that manipulated the normal competition process in the pharmaceutical market.⁵² The EUCJ reviewed whether pharmaceutical products without authorization can be sold on the same relevant market as products with approval. Because Avastin's off-label prescription was not legally established, the court found it belonged in the same market as Lucentis.⁵³ Colangelo⁵⁴ argues that restriction by object analysis about off-label use of drugs and disparagement practices in the pharmaceutical sector should be done on a case-by-case basis.

Regulatory gaps in the EU pharmaceutical regulations may lead to competition law violations. Papadopoulou (2022) suggests that the current regulatory system governing supplementary protection certificates (SPC) in the pharmaceutical market and the lack of adequate regulations could violate patients' rights and increase the number of anti-competitive practices.⁵⁵ Obtaining SPC through misusing the regulatory system in the

⁴⁷ Frederick M Abbott, *Using Competition Law to Promote Access to Health Technologies: A Supplement to the Guidebook for Low-and Middle-Income Countries* (UNDP 2022).

⁴⁸ French Competition Authority, *Sanofi-Aventis Belgium SA (limited) C-472/07*, 14 January 2010 (Joined cases C-471/07 and C-472/07)

⁴⁹ European Commission Press Release, 'Antitrust: Commission open investigation into possible anticompetitive disparagement by Vifor pharma of iron medicine' 20 June 2022 <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/sl/ip_22_3882> accessed 14 June 2024.

⁵⁰ Alexandr Svetlicinni, 'Off Label Use of Medicines under Scrutiny, between Competition Law and Pharma Regulation' (2019) 38 *Medicine Law* 165, 167.

⁵¹ Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 23 January 2018, *F Hoffmann-La Roche Ltd and Others v Autorità Garante della Concorrenza e del Mercato*, C-179/16 Hoffmann-La Roche [2018], paras 94–95.

⁵² Autorità Garante della Concorrenza e del Mercato (AGCM) [2014] <<https://www.agcm.it/media/comunicati-stampa/2014/3/alias-6801>> accessed 14 June 2024.

⁵³ Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 23 January 2018, *F Hoffmann-La Roche Ltd and Others v Autorità Garante della Concorrenza e del Mercato*, C-179/16 Hoffmann-La Roche [2018], paras 94–95.

⁵⁴ Margherita Colangelo, 'The Dissemination of Misleading Information in the Pharmaceutical Market: The Italian Experience' in Wolf Sauter, Marcel Canoy and Jotte Muler (eds), *EU Competition Law and Pharmaceuticals* (Edward Elgar 2022) 209.

⁵⁵ Frantzeska Papadopoulou, 'Evergreening Exclusive Rights in Pharmaceutical Products: The Case of SPCs, Pediatric Extensions and Orphan Drugs' in Wolf Sauter, Marcel Canoy and Jotte Muler (eds), *EU Competition Law and Pharmaceuticals* (Edward Elgar 2022) 47.

In the EU, temporary measures to facilitate the supply of essential goods were adopted and updated during the pandemic. The ‘Temporary Framework Communication’⁶³ issued by the European Commission on 8 April 2020, is an example of a pragmatic and flexible approach⁶⁴ during the COVID-19 outbreak. Some behaviours that typically violate EU competition law were, to some extent, acceptable in the COVID-19 era. The Framework mentioned that undertakings could cooperate and coordinate their practices to ensure that essential goods are available to meet the increased demand, provided that their activities do not breach EU competition law. Furthermore, the cooperation must be limited, proportionate, and temporary and serve the interests of consumers and the general public. The joint practices of competitors based on this framework must be transparent, and crisis cannot be used as a cover for exploiting consumers, anti-competitive collusions, and abusing dominance. A set of safeguards and monitoring mechanisms are also anticipated in the Framework. This flexible approach did not ignore the danger of anticompetitive practices, such as excessive pricing, horizontal anticompetitive agreements, or market foreclosure, even in a health crisis. Despite its flexible approach, the European Commission and national competition authorities remained committed to combating anticompetitive practices and agreements during the pandemic. Although Article 102 TFEU used to prohibit abuse of a dominant market position, and traditionally, this applies to the undertakings with a lasting hold on the market in case of crises like the COVID-19 pandemic and the emergence of a ‘situational monopoly’, where a company dominates a market temporarily, as Costa-Cabral and others suggest, Article 102 TFEU may also apply to combat the virus-profiteering of some market players, especially when they have new technology and try to squeeze out their competitors by creating barriers to entry.⁶⁵ Some of the reasons for this flexible approach are explained in the Commission’s 2024 report, including ‘the crucial role of the health sector businesses’, especially in ‘mitigating the effects of the crisis’, also ‘exceptional circumstances and a need for companies to cooperate’, ‘to ensure supply and fair distribution of essential and possibly scarce products and services’.⁶⁶

Some examples of the reaction to competition law infringements during the pandemic include the Dutch NCA investigating Roche Diagnostics for not providing the formula for a key component of its PCR COVID-19 tests. This led to the removal of restrictions and the increase in the capacity to produce this specific pandemic-related product.⁶⁷ Another successful crisis initiative by NCAs was the approval of a ‘VCI Emergency Platform for Vaccination Equipment’ to coordinate vaccine supply, including syringes, cannulas, and NaCl solutions in Germany. This initiative focused on the emergency-only approach, and data and price sharing were limited based on this.⁶⁸

The Commission provides comfort letters to undertakings to ensure their proposed actions do not violate competition law; comfort letters are an old EU competition law tradition⁶⁹ that was revived during the pandemic (eg issuing a comfort letter to Medicines for

⁶³ Communication From the Commission, Temporary Framework for assessing antitrust issues related to business cooperation in response to situations of urgency stemming from the current COVID-19 outbreak, Brussels, 8.4.2020 C(2020) 3200 final.

⁶⁴ Marciej M Sokolowski, ‘Regulation in the COVID-19 Pandemic and Post-pandemic Times, Day Watchman Tackling the Novel Coronavirus’ (2020) 10 TGPPP 211.

⁶⁵ Costa-Cabral and others (n 10) 11.

⁶⁶ European Commission (n 21) 20–22.

⁶⁷ Authority for Consumers & Markets (3 April 2020). ACM has confidence in Roche’s commitment to help solve problems with test materials. ACM <<https://www.acm.nl/en/publications/acm-has-confidence-commitments-made-roche-help-solve-problems-test-materials>> accessed 14 June 2024. see also: European Commission (n 21) 21–22.

⁶⁸ Bundeskartellamt, ‘Bundeskartellamt gives green light for Emergency Platform for Vaccination Equipment—Also no objection to the participation of pharmaceutical wholesalers’ *Press Release*, 29 March <https://www.bundeskartellamt.de/SharedDocs/Meldung/EN/Pressemitteilungen/2021/29_03_2021_Impfzubehoer_Plattform.html> accessed 14 June 2024. See also Commission Pharma Report (2024) 21–22.

⁶⁹ Henry and Buhart (n 14).

can help.⁸¹ He argues that ‘the disapplication of the competition rules via a so-called public policy exemption (introduced after the initial stages of the pandemic) was not in the consumer interest’⁸² also, this kind of cooperation can sometimes form durable and stable agreements even after the crisis, and the US’s experience in battling the Great Depression proves this claim.⁸³

It seems that the Commission faced difficult trade-offs between preserving competition, protecting consumers, promoting economic stability, and supporting the continuity of essential services during the pandemic. Considering the unique circumstances of the crisis, the Commission made decisions based on a soft-law-based approach. Although these changes were substantially based on multiple temporary-based frameworks, cover letters and soft law were revised or withdrawn after the (health) crisis phase. The Commission and the national competition authorities had not planned to permit the collaboration between undertakings after the crisis phase. However, controlling the road of exchanging data and collaborating that once was open seems complicated (if not impossible).

Another aspect of the pandemic was dealing with state aid in the pharmaceutical sector. The objective of state aid control is not specific to competition⁸⁴ and can be used effectively during times of crisis. As a result of the COVID-19 outbreak, state aid control in the health sector has undergone revisions and modifications. During the pandemic, the EU promoted state aid, particularly for health products. A ‘Temporary Framework for State Aid’⁸⁵ was adopted on 19 March 2020, to allow Member States to take advantage of all the flexibility state aid regulations provide. The legal basis for the pandemic state aid at the beginning of the Pandemic was Article 107(2) b TFEU,⁸⁶ and after the situation changed and became more severe, the legal basis changed to Article 107(3) TFEU.⁸⁷

The temporary framework was modified six times and extended until 30 June 2022. Based on this framework, 1350 decisions and more than 980 national measures (approximately €3.2 trillion) were adopted.⁸⁸ Several of these decisions dealt with the pharmaceutical industry. Temporary measures and state aid framework allowed Member States to provide financial support to pharmaceutical undertakings through grants, loans, guarantees, or tax incentives. Biondi⁸⁹ assesses the European Commission’s temporary framework on state aid, the effectiveness of the measures taken, and the ability of Member States to take appropriate actions in this regard. A European Parliament report on the ‘Impact of State Aid on Competition and Competitiveness during the COVID-19 Pandemic’⁹⁰ calls for the Commission to improve transparency in evaluating state aid cases. This report’s recommendation includes a more precise articulation of the motivations and conditions for case approval and consideration of earlier submissions made by the same Member State or comparable submissions made by other Member States during the evaluation process. It also proposes a differentiated approach to evaluating smaller and more significant cases to mitigate excessive administrative challenges. In addition, the report emphasizes the significance

⁸¹ B Wardhaugh, *Competition Law in Crisis: The Antitrust Response to Economic Shocks* (CUP 2022) 67.

⁸² *ibid* 147.

⁸³ *ibid* 143.

⁸⁴ Leigh Hancher and Juan J Piernas López, eds. *Research Handbook on European State Aid Law* (Edward Elgar 2021) 1.

⁸⁵ Communication from the Commission Temporary Framework for State aid measures to support the economy in the current COVID-19 Outbreak 2020/C 91 I/01, C/2020/1863, OJ C 911, 20.3.2020, 1-9.

⁸⁶ ‘aid to make good the damage caused by natural disasters or exceptional occurrences’.

⁸⁷ ‘aid to promote the execution of an important project of common European interest or to remedy a serious disturbance in the economy of a Member State’.

⁸⁸ <https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-06/Temporary_framework.pdf> accessed 25 May 2024.

⁸⁹ Andrea Biondi, ‘Governing the Interregnum: State Aid Rules and the Covid-19 Crisis’ (2020) IV Market Compet LR 17.

⁹⁰ Jan Van Hove, ‘Impact of state aid on competition and competitiveness during the COVID-19 pandemic: an early assessment’ (2020) Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, Directorate-General for Internal Policies, European Parliament 38–39.

of a more thorough screening of umbrella deals submitted by large Member States.⁹¹ The long-lasting impacts of the pandemic are still felt in post-pandemic, a newly approved €1 billion for state aid for the first ‘Important Project of Common European Interest in the Health Sector’ to support ‘research, innovation, and the first industrial deployment of health-care products, as well as innovative production processes of pharmaceuticals’,⁹² is an example of continued flexibility in state aid in the health sector.

Public procurement (PP) is another issue brought to the forefront by the crisis. As Sanchez-Graells (2015)⁹³ mentioned, competition considerations have always played a natural role in public procurement.⁹⁴ Anticompetitive practices, such as excessive pricing and bid-rigging, threaten the procurement process. These risks are especially acute during crises. During the pandemic, public procurement policies were changed and modified to facilitate the timely and efficient procurement of crisis-related products (specifically pharmaceutical products). Among the various actions taken, specific procurement rules were eased, simplifying the process for businesses to participate in bidding and negotiations.⁹⁵

The availability of vaccines for Europeans was also one of the Commission’s missions during the pandemic. The Commission secured advance purchase agreements⁹⁶ with vaccine manufacturers and took some steps to facilitate the rapid approval and distribution of vaccines. McEvoy and Ferri analyse the European Joint Procurement Agreement (JPA) during the COVID-19 pandemic and how it has helped Member States strengthen their buying power and enjoy the benefits of economies of scale. However, the transparency of the pricing mechanism⁹⁷ that the authors claimed was not obvious in the contracts with vaccine manufacturers. COVID-19 Vaccine manufacturers consider themselves ‘the pandemic champions’, and vaccine contracts with these undertakings were utterly confidential. One of Pfizer’s leaked vaccine agreements shows several confidentiality clauses. Furthermore, the negotiations with vaccine manufacturers during the pandemic did not follow the official public procurement procedures, transparency, and accountability concerns about pandemic champions.

The COVID-19 pandemic presented challenges in the current competition law system, state aid and public procurement in the health sector, including the need for more transparency. This was exemplified by the negotiation process of purchasing the COVID-19 vaccine between the European Commission’s president and Pfizer’s CEO, conducted mainly through unusual negotiating tools such as SMS.⁹⁸ As a result of the European Ombudsman’s investigation, Pfizer’s CEO was invited to the European Parliament hearing. However, he did not attend the hearing.⁹⁹ The WHO Guidance Report (2016), derived from consultations with Member States and key partners, noted that some features, such as transparency,

⁹¹ *ibid* 38–39.

⁹² Commission approves up to €1 billion of State aid by six Member States for the first Important Project of Common European Interest in the health sector <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_24_2852> accessed 14 June 2024.

⁹³ Albert Sanchez-Graells, *Public procurement and the EU competition rules*. (Bloomsbury Publishing 2015).

⁹⁴ Sanchez-Graells, in another work (2020), focuses on some of the increasing concerns in the procurement response to COVID-19 and the post-pandemic challenges in this regard from a regulatory point of view, See Sanchez-Graells, ‘Procurement in the Time of COVID-19’ (2020) 71 NILQ 81.

⁹⁵ Emma McEvoy, ‘Procuring in a Pandemic: Assessing the Use of the EU Public Procurement Directives, the Joint Procurement Agreement and Advance Purchase Agreements’ (2022) 73 NILQ 260.

⁹⁶ See ‘Commission Decision on approving the agreement with Member States on procuring Covid-19 vaccines on behalf of the Member States and related procedures’ (18 June 2020) <https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-09/decision_approving_the_agreement_with_member_states_on_procuring_covid_19_vaccines_on_behalf_of_the_member_states_and_related_procedures.pdf> accessed 14 June 2024.

⁹⁷ For an overview of the principle of transparency and the effects of this principle, See C Bovis (ed), ‘The Principle of Public Procurement Regulation’ in *Research Handbook on EU Public Procurement Law* (Edward Elgar 2016) 35–46.

⁹⁸ See Matina Stevis-Gridneff ‘How Europe Sealed a Pfizer Vaccine Deal with Texts and Calls’ *New York Times* (New York City 2021) 28.

⁹⁹ Politico, ‘Pfizer CEO pulls out of testifying to EU Parliament COVID panel’ <<https://www.politico.eu/article/pfizer-ceo-albert-bourla-pulls-out-of-testifying-to-eu-parliament-covid-panel/>> accessed 14 June 2024.

This strategy covers some key elements, such as ‘Access to safe medicine’, one of the pillars of the previously introduced ‘European Health Union’.¹²⁶ The unmet needs of the patients (especially rare diseases), the limitation of investment in this area, revising the legislation regarding ‘medicines for children and rare diseases’,¹²⁷ and ‘facilitating collaboration on unmet needs’, ‘Pilot innovative approaches to the EU research and development and public procurement for antimicrobials and their alternatives’,¹²⁸ promoting ‘investment and coordinating research, development, manufacturing, deployment and use for new antibiotics as part of the new EU Health Emergency Response Authority’, and introducing ‘new measures to restrict and optimise the use of antimicrobial medicines’ are among initiatives of the Strategy related to the antimicrobial resistance.¹²⁹

Optimizing the SPC system according to the ‘Intellectual Support Action Plan’, establishing an ‘interoperable data access infrastructure for the European health data space’ by 2025,¹³⁰ and supporting ‘public-private and public-public partnership’ are some of the strategies’ flagship initiatives regarding competitiveness. Regarding innovation, ‘enhancing dialogue among authorities’ and ‘promoting artificial intelligence use in this sector’ are among the pharmaceutical strategy’s proposals.¹³¹ Issuing appropriate policies for supporting ‘greater generic and biosimilar competition’,¹³² ‘removal of barriers to entry into the market’, and emphasis on the ‘enforcement of the EU competition rules’ are also mentioned in the strategy.¹³³ The Strategy also stressed the importance of transparency in R&D costs and improving the ‘public procurement process of pharmaceuticals’, which were very important during COVID-19. The Commission has announced its intention to unveil a revised pharmaceutical package in 2023.

The European Commission’s adaptation of the New Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe highlights the importance of ensuring patients have access to innovative and affordable drugs. Balancing these two competing goals can be challenging, as the cost of R&D must be recouped for the industry to remain sustainable. The strategy aims to improve competition between generic and biosimilar products by removing barriers to entry. It also emphasizes transparency in research and development costs and seeks to revise the supplementary protection certificate system, which could lead to a more transparent and competitive pharmaceutical sector. This strategy can impact competition law in this sector as it highlights the delicate balance between competition policy, affordability of drugs, enhancing the competition between biosimilars, generics and branded products and intellectual property protection.

Pharmaceutical Reform Package

The Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe set a framework to reform the European pharmaceutical regulations and the Pharmaceutical Reform Package followed it.¹³⁴ On 26 April

¹²⁶ European Health Union Package: COM (2020), 124, COM (2020) 725, COM (2020) 720, COM (2020) 727, for a study regarding challenges of a European Health Union, See Mary Guy, ‘Towards a European Health Union: What Role for Member States?’ (2020) 11 Eur J Risk Regul 757, and for a Joint Statement on Inclusive Pharmaceutical Strategy, See Éloïse Gennet and others, ‘Health as a Fundamental Value. Towards an Inclusive and Equitable Pharmaceutical Strategy for the European Union’, Report, European Health Policy Platform of the European Commission (2022) <<https://shs.hal.science/halshs-03780394/>> accessed 18 June 2024.

¹²⁷ See G Vassal and others, ‘Access to Essential Anticancer Medicines for Children and Adolescents in Europe’ (2021) 32 Ann Oncol 560.

¹²⁸ Pharmaceutical Strategy (n 125) 6.

¹²⁹ For recommendations regarding antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the Strategy, See Gennet and others (n 126) 28–29.

¹³⁰ Pharmaceutical Strategy (n 125) 11

¹³¹ *ibid* 15.

¹³² For recommendations regarding Generics and biosimilars, See Gennet and others (n 126) 29.

¹³³ Pharmaceutical Strategy (n 125) 7.

¹³⁴ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL laying down Union procedures for the authorization and supervision of medicinal products for human use and establishing rules governing the European Medicines Agency, amending Regulation (EC) No 1394/2007 and Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 726/2004, Regulation (EC) No 141/2000, and Regulation (EC) No 1901/2006 L.

2023, the Commission announced the adaptation of a new regulation and directive proposal to reform the current EU pharmaceutical legislation after 20 years. This reform will significantly impact the pharmaceutical sector in line with the EU pharmaceutical strategy and strive to improve the ‘accessibility, availability, and affordability’ of medicines across EU Member States, particularly for those patients with ‘rare diseases’ or ‘unmet medical needs’. One of the aspects of this reform that will impact competition law is the emphasis on high prices for innovative medicines and the costs of patented drugs for patients and health systems. The new pharmaceutical regulation will affect the relationship between originators with generics and biosimilar producers and help design a more patient-centred pharmaceutical sector. The proposal specifically mentioned these products’ simplified availability and earlier availability.

The proposal also highlighted the need to strengthen the competitiveness of the EU pharmaceutical industry globally and improve the EU’s standing as a leader in the biopharmaceutical market by engaging in ‘digital transformation and new technologies’. It also aims to create a ‘single market for medicines’ to achieve the goals of effectiveness, affordability, and accessibility. The proposal also seeks to simplify the review process and shorten the approval time for pharmaceuticals. This will result in patients having more rapid access to medicine. It will lay the groundwork for creating a patient-centric and forward-focused pharmaceutical system, allowing the EU industry to lead the way in medical innovation. The pharmaceutical package, comprising 55 action points, aims to create a patient-centred and forward-thinking pharmaceutical system; it also includes non-legislative actions that, through information sharing, aim to improve Member State collaboration on pricing, reimbursement, and procurement laws.¹³⁵ However, as Plank¹³⁶ argues that COVID-19 was only an accelerator in these reforms, and the impact of the pandemic showed the ugly face of market failure in this sector. All the solidarity-based and patient-centred pharmaceutical sectors made more sense after COVID-19.

Proposal for a regulation on compulsory licensing for crisis management¹³⁷

On 27 April 2023, the Commission published a proposal for compulsory licensing. This proposal will impact patent law, crisis management and competition law, and the commission aims to increase EU resilience in case of future crises and increase the accessibility of pandemic-related products by using compulsory licensing as an effective tool. The proposal also seeks to improve competitiveness by empowering small- and medium-sized undertakings to use the technology of big pharmaceutical companies in the framework of compulsory licensing, which is supposed to be a valuable tool in an emergency. Compulsory licensing allows governments to license patented technologies under certain conditions without the rightsholder’s consent. There is a national-level framework for compulsory licensing in each Member State. Still, its shortcomings became apparent during the pandemic, and the pressure from civil society, NGOs and the general public and the fact that people blame IP holders for pandemic-related products were some reasons that accelerated the approval of these new regulations. The legal basis of this proposal is Articles 114 and 207 of TFEU.

The proposed pharmaceutical legislation recommends suspending both data and marketing exclusivity protections during public health emergencies. It impacts competition law by enabling generic manufacturers to utilize the original regulatory test data to approve generic versions, decreasing the market entry obstacles for these producers and increasing access to

¹³⁵ Commission Pharma Report (2024) 19.

¹³⁶ Kristine Plank, ‘COVID-19, Geopolitics, and the Reform of European Pharmaceutical Law: Accelerating Enhanced Medicines Care for Europe?’ (2024) 12 *Med Res Arch* 1, 2.

¹³⁷ Commission, ‘Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on compulsory licensing for crisis management and amending Regulation (EC) 816/2006’ COM (2023) 224 final.

machines for all. McMahon¹³⁸ mentioned that based on the current proposal, this framework only applies to EU-wide crises and does not consider emergencies affecting individual Member States. EU could terminate the compulsory licensing framework when the crisis mode ends at the EU level, possibly causing a sudden loss of access to related products. It must make sense for generic pharmaceutical producers to invest in a temporary basis framework.

Single Market Emergency Instrument

On 19 September 2022, EU Commissioner M Vestager announced the Single Market Emergency Instrument (SMEI) proposal in a press release titled ‘Crisis-proofing the single market’.¹³⁹ This governance framework aims to ease the crisis management of the single market and allows European policymakers to react efficiently and effectively to future crises. In the impending crisis, SMEI aims to complement other EU rules and ‘ensure the free movement of goods and people’. When an interruption occurs in the supply chain, SMEI anticipates some actions. The key novelty of this initiative is the anticipation of three modes: contingency, vigilance and emergency modes. The Commission is responsible for ‘activating the vigilance mode’, and in case of disruption (such as a global pandemic or war that has a wide-ranging impact), the European Council has the power to activate the emergency mode.

The SMEI proposed the establishment of an advisory group consisting of representatives from the commission and Member States. The advisory group would be empowered, through the authority of the Commission, to prohibit or approve the circulation of critical goods or require undertakings to disclose certain information. The SMEI envisaged some extraordinary measures under the emergency mode that would necessitate stricter procedural mechanisms, which would be activated by a subsequent Commission implementing Act (dual activation). These procedures must be put in place in a given industry. Such actions would always be done following consultation with that sector and submitting a voluntary request.

In discussing the SMEA, some Member States expressed concerns about how a crisis is defined and Member States’ involvement in the process.¹⁴⁰ They stressed the importance of clearly communicating the temporary and urgent nature of the crisis definition in the policy. In the same vein, Linden argued that SMEI should not impose an unnecessary burden on undertakings which were under pressure because of the pandemic and the obligations imposed on companies (as proposed by the SMEI), should be subject to a proportionality test,¹⁴¹ according to Article 5 TEU (the Treaty on EU).¹⁴² Bardt and others believe that this instrument can lead to normalizing ‘the state control in private ownership’ and ‘war economy structure’ and is also ineffective in severing ties with third countries in a crisis.¹⁴³

¹³⁸ Aisling McMahon, ‘EU’s Compulsory Licensing Proposals, Patents and Crisis Preparedness—Some Steps in the Right Direction but More to Do for Future Pandemic Preparedness’ (*JME Blog*, 2023) <<https://blogs.bmj.com/medical-ethics/2023/05/04/eus-compulsory-licensing-proposals-patents-and-crisis-preparedness-some-steps-in-the-right-direction-but-more-to-do-for-future-pandemic-preparedness>> accessed 18 June 2024

¹³⁹ ‘Crisis-proofing the Single market: equipping Europe with a robust toolbox to preserve free movement and availability of relevant goods and services’ the European Commission press release, 19 September 2022 <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_5443> accessed 14 June 2024.

¹⁴⁰ See ‘Considerations by Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Ireland, Netherlands, Slovenia and Sweden on a Single Market Emergency Instrument’ <<https://open.overheid.nl/repository/oep-81b8e60f1a12c5af348345471ac96a23222faa17/1/pdf/blg-1041239.pdf>> accessed 18 June 2024.

¹⁴¹ Olivier Linden, ‘Lessons from the Pandemic-Designing a Single Market Crisis Management Mechanism’ (2022) *Kommerskollegium* 34 <<https://www.kommerskollegium.se/globalassets/publikationer/rapporter/2022/lessons-from-the-pandemic.pdf>> accessed 18 June 2024.

¹⁴² Consolidated version of the Treaty on European Union Article 5 (ex-Article 5 TEC), Official Journal 115, 09/05/2008 P. 0018–0018.

¹⁴³ Hubertus Bardt and others, ‘Single Market Emergency Instrument: Ein Instrument mit Tücken. No 7/2022’ IW-Policy Paper, 2022.

The new instrument will generally change the laws and regulations already in place. However, The SMEI proposal clarifies that this regulation does not affect Union competition rules, including antitrust, merger, and state aid rules. Still, it may influence the EU policies on compulsory pharmaceutical licensing, especially during a health crisis. During the next crisis, measures may be issued to regulate cooperation and collaboration among businesses in different markets, including the health sector, with regard to competition law. Companies not complying with SMEI regulations may be fined 1.5% of their daily turnover. In June 2023, the EU Council published its opinions on SMEI, and in July of the same year, the European Parliament adopted its first reading. In February 2024, the Council and the European Parliament reached a provisional agreement on the SMEI's regulation. After this agreement, the SMEI will be renamed the Internal Market Emergency and Resilience Act (IMERA).¹⁴⁴

The Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority

The Health Emergency Preparedness and Response (HERA) is a new European Commission Directorate-General created in September 2021 to anticipate threats and health crises through intelligence gathering and response capacity building. It complements similar agencies such as the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), the European Commission Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG-SANTE), and the European Medicines Agency (EMA).¹⁴⁵ Like its US version, BARDA (Biomedical Advanced Research and Development Authority), HERA's duties include maintaining a stockpile of necessary medical supplies and equipment and sponsoring relevant health and development research.¹⁴⁶ The creation of HERA was a timely and critical step in addressing the COVID-19 pandemic and being cautious and prepared for future health crises, including pandemics and environmental and antimicrobial resistance crises.¹⁴⁷ Shroff and others (2022) suggested that HERA collaborate with WHO as an international moderator to remove current barriers in the health sector and promote procurement transparency for pharmaceuticals. Furthermore, they emphasize the importance of patient involvement in regulation and HERA's role in this process.¹⁴⁸ HERA has a critical role in enforcing 'The European Health Union',¹⁴⁹ and some of its responsibilities are related to competition law. HERA's position as a new regulatory authority can impact the enforcement of competition law in the pharmaceutical sector, especially regarding transparency in public procurement in the health sector and maintaining a stockpile of essential medical supplies that may affect the pharmaceutical market. Monitoring and regulating the stockpile of pandemic-related products can prevent hoarding or other anticompetitive practices in the pharmaceutical market and ensure equitable access to medical supplies. Promoting patient-centred policies from HERA can increase competition by incentivizing undertakings to produce medicines that address patients' needs and preferences. This will lead to a more competitive pharmaceutical industry.

¹⁴⁴ SMEI / IMERA: Council and Parliament strike a provisional deal on crisis preparedness <<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/02/01/single-market-emergency-instrument-council-and-parliament-strike-a-provisional-deal-on-crisis-preparedness/>> accessed 14 June 2024.

¹⁴⁵ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and The Committee of the Regions, Introducing HERA, the European Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority, the next step towards completing the European Health Union, 16.9.2021. COM (2021) 576 final.

¹⁴⁶ Michael Anderson, Rebecca Forman and Elias Mossialos, 'Navigating the role of the EU Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA) in Europe and Beyond' (2021) 9, TLRH, 1-4.

¹⁴⁷ Pierre Delsaux, 'Preparing Europe for future health threats and crises—the European Health Emergency and Preparedness Authority; improving EU preparedness and response in the area of medical countermeasures', (2022) 27 *Eurosurveillance* 1, 2.

¹⁴⁸ Zublin C Shroff and others, 'Time to Reconceptualise Health Systems' (2021) 397 *Lancet Reg* 2145, 2147.

¹⁴⁹ European Health Union Package: COM (2020), 124, COM (2020) 725, COM (2020) 720, COM (2020) 727.

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